

Essential metal elements content in rice in Henan province of China

Qinghua Yan^{a*}, Li Yang^{b,c}, Yanlan Li^a and Guoxi Xi^c

^aDepartment of Life Science and Technology, Xinxiang Medical University, Xinxiang Henan 453003, P. R. China

E-mail : yqh3499@aliyun.com *Fax* : 86-373-3040015

^bDepartment of Experimental Center, Henan Institute of Science and Technology, Xinxiang Henan 453003, P. R. China

^cSchool of Environment, School of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Henan Normal University 453007, P. R. China

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Abstract : An analytical method using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) for rapid simultaneous determination of twelve essential metal elements (Fe, Mg, Mn, Se, Ni, Cu, K, Na, Ca, Zn, Co and Cr) in nine rice was performed. The pretreatment of the sample was also studied using a single microwave program by digesting extraction. The optimum operating conditions and wavelength emitted by twelve different elements were selected using the sensitivity and recovery of mixed standard solutions as criterions. The standard reference materials GBW10010 rice was used in order to verify the accuracy of the method and the results were in excellent agreement with the certified values. The uncertainties and concentration of constituent elements were determined and the possibility of their use in the quality control was considered.

Keywords : Essential elements, rice, microwave digestion, ICP-OES.

Introduction

Among those metal elements, some are known to be essential for humans in a specific concentration range, like Mn, Cu, Fe and Cr, however in higher concentration can be toxic to humans or in lower level may cause serious disorders of human body and functions¹⁻⁵. Essential metal elements play an important role in promote the body's growth and development and prevention disease, and even life-threatening. Quantification of essential metal elements in human body fluids is important in the diagnosis and treatment of a range of disorders, and also in forensic medicine⁸. Therefore, people will choose food of high element concentrations to adjust diet according each person's own situation.

Rice is the most important contributor to the global food basket and plays a major role in irrigated agriculture. In China, most people take rice as the main food, the rice contains a number of essential metal elements and minerals. Pathways by which trace elements can enter rice mainly include artificial fertilizers and irrigation

water applied for rice plant growth. The main source of irrigation water is the Yellow River, the Yellow River provides an important guarantee for wet conditions for the growth of rice in Xinxiang. The environmental evidence from the Yellow River field of Xinxiang not only establishes the presence of extremely early dedicated rice cultivation but allows an assessment of the earliest Xinxiang rice cultivation system itself. It is extremely important to us to know the content of essential metal elements in these rice types.

A multitude of treatments are used to prepare samples for determination of elements⁹. The basic modes of treatment of the analytical sample are most often a wet digestion method or dry ashing method to remove the organic matrix and retain the analytes of interest in a solution for introduction into the analytical instrument^{10,11}. Dry ashing method is destruction of the organic matter by high temperature and a traditional means of treatment for the determination of Pb, Cd and other elements. However, Fecher and Ruhnke¹² had Cd and Pb cross-contamination

issues during dry ashing and low recoveries of Al and Pb by dry ashing have been reported by Moeller *et al.*¹³. Wet digestion method is digestion of the sample with either acid or bases, referred to as the “wet ashing”. Wet digestion method assisted by microwaves is a frequently used treatment procedure for multi-element analysis of food¹⁴. Dolan and Capar¹⁵ developed a microwave digestion procedure for multi-element analysis of food by ICP-OES that allows the use of a single microwave program by digesting a mass that varies depending on energy content of the food. ICP-OES is becoming prevalent throughout the world as the instrument of choice for monitoring the levels of metal elements in food.

The aim of our work was to develop the ICP-OES and microwave digestion procedure and for rapid monitoring of essential elements concentrations in rice samples from different rice plant areas, which would provides a theoretical basis for people to choose a diet to supplement its essential metal elements.

Results and discussion

Method validation :

Procedural blanks :

The mean blank value was deducted from the readings before the result was calculated. The batch blank was used to decide if the results of the batch were acceptable or not, i.e. if the blank gave a significant contribution to the result the batch was reanalyzed¹⁶.

Analysis of standard reference materials :

The accuracy and precision of the method were tested with a standard reference materials GBW10010 rice. The results of the standard reference materials GBW10010 rice analyzed throughout this survey are shown in Table 1. The results showed that the content of essential elements were in agreement (within $\pm 10\%$) with the certified values. According to the results showed the relative standard deviations of all the elements tested were not more than 5% and good agreement of measured values and assured that the accuracy and precision of the method were good.

Determination of essential metal elements in nine rice samples :

Essential metal elements concentrations were analyzed in rice samples by ICP-OES. The contents of essential

Table 1. Analysis of standard reference materials GBW10010 rice ($n = 6$)

Element	GBW10010 rice (mg/kg)		RSD (%)
	Certified value	Measure value	
Fe	7.6	7.82	3.29
Mg	410	434.6	4.10
Mn	17	16.6	3.46
Se	0.061	0.058	4.41
Ni	0.27	0.26	2.87
Cu	4.9	5.12	1.62
K	1380	1365	3.81
Na	25	23	4.07
Ca	110	99	3.52
Zn	23	25	3.11
Co	0.01	0.012	4.39
Cr	0.09	0.086	4.28

metal elements in the different rice samples are presented in Table 2.

Iron :

Iron is absolutely essential to life. It is a required part of hemoglobin, myoglobin, ferredoxins, cytochromes and several enzymes active in porphyrin synthesis, oxygen regulation and immunity. The average iron content in all rice samples was 49.22 mg/kg (range from 12.21–252.5 mg/kg). This was markedly higher than the results of Koivistoinen who reported mean levels of 12 mg/kg in white rice¹⁷. But our result was markedly lower than the results of Gorbunov *et al.*¹⁸ who reported a mean level of 137 mg/kg in rice from the Astrakhan region of Russia. However, the mean iron level of 60.28 mg/kg in rice from Fucun and Hongjingzui of huojia was higher than the mean iron level of 27.10 mg/kg in rice from Taiping collage of yuanyang.

Magnesium :

Magnesium is the main component of various enzyme in human body. Magnesium is involved in RNA and deoxyribonucleic acid synthesis and involved in neuromuscular conduction. The magnesium levels showed much variation, ranging from 191.85 to 1034.51 mg/kg among the three regions. The mean magnesium level in Fucun of huojia (208.34 mg/kg) was lower than the content in Hongjingzui of huojia (465.55 mg/kg) and Taiping collage of yuanyang (989.74 mg/kg). It is however known there are differences between the three regions, e.g. cul-

Table 2. Concentration of essential metal elements in nine rice samples (mean mg/kg, $n = 5$)

Element	Fucun of huojia			Hongjingzui of huojia			Taiping collage of yuanyang		
	Shengdao 16	Xinfeng 4	Xinfeng 2	Huangjinqing	Xinfeng 2	Zhengdao 19	Zhengdao 19	Xinfeng 2	Huangjinxiu
Fe	252.5	17.12	17.65	13.75	24.15	36.51	20.15	12.21	48.95
Mg	191.85	227.65	205.53	214.21	973.52	208.92	1034.51	912.21	1022.51
Mn	7.71	6.83	6.71	7.72	32.82	6.75	22.91	15.52	17.91
Se	2.75	2.35	2.45	2.25	4.32	2.41	2.80	4.25	3.05
Ni	22.95	0.65	0.45	0.75	0.25	0.41	0.45	1.05	1.35
Cu	5.35	4.42	4.81	5.31	4.82	4.75	5.12	4.65	5.42
K	474.89	432.10	620.41	414.40	550.15	283.95	821.05	940.96	473.99
Na	275.82	221.78	318.99	256.99	248.86	222.93	229.75	261.28	226.23
Ca	147.58	119.14	91.90	84.78	115.45	83.24	115.53	106.32	66.55
Zn	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Co	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Cr	1.99	1.75	1.46	2.21	2.36	1.65	1.51	1.41	1.01

ND : Not detected.

tivars, place of origin etc., that could explain the higher Mg levels in Taiping collage of yuanyang.

Nickel :

Nickel can stimulate the growth of blood and the regeneration of red cells. In the human body is short of copper, nickel physiological activity will give full play to human body, and does not affect the physiological activity of copper. The average content of nickel in rice of Fucun of huojia was 8.02 mg/kg (range = 0.45–22.95 mg/kg). The mean nickel level of 0.47 mg/kg and 0.95 mg/kg in Hongjingzui of huojia and Taiping collage of yuanyang were lower than the content in Fucun of huojia.

Copper :

Copper is one of the human body needs of mineral elements, copper deficiency can cause anaemia, hair keratinization, arterial elasticity, and mental retardation. The copper levels showed little variation, ranging from 4.42 to 5.42 mg/kg, with a mean of 4.96 mg/kg, and no significant difference among the three regions. From several recent studies similar levels have been reported, ranging between 2 and 5 mg/kg¹⁹⁻²². However, the mean copper level of 4.96 mg/kg in rice was markedly higher than the result of Jorhem *et al.* (the mean level of 1.9 mg/kg in rice produced in Asia)²³.

Manganese :

Manganese is often considered to be among the least toxic of the trace elements when administered orally. Diets

high in unrefined cereals, nuts, leafy vegetables and tea will be high in manganese. Manganese is both an activator and a constituent of several enzymes like hydrolases, kinases, decarboxylases and transferases. The overall average content of manganese in rice was 13.88 mg/kg (range = 6.71–32.82 mg/kg). The mean manganese level of 7.08 mg/kg (range = 6.71–7.7 mg/kg) in Fucun of huojia was lower than the content in Hongjingzui of huojia and Taiping collage of yuanyang, with means of 42.82 and 18.78 mg/kg. Results from Viet Nam with means of 9.9–13.6 mg/kg for rice¹⁹, together with results from Finland reporting means of 9 mg/kg for white rice¹⁷.

Manganese is a minor element in rice but it appears to be an important one, interestingly the significance of manganese in rice grain is not an isolated case, because this element was found to be the significant indicator for the discrimination of coffees on the basis of their geographical origin²⁴.

Selenium :

Selenium is of fundamental importance for human health including a proper function of the immune system, prevention of cardiovascular diseases and inflammations. Deficiency of selenium can increase viral infections. The overall mean selenium content was 2.96 mg/kg. The observed levels were higher than previously reported selenium concentrations in rice. Jorhem *et al.* and Kelly *et al.*^{23,25} found a range of 0.00–0.40 mg/kg in rice from

Asia, Europe and USA. As to the three regions, the mean selenium level in Fucun of huojia was lower than the content in Hongjingzui of huojia and Taiping collage of yuanyang.

Chromium :

Chromium is an important element for the normal growth and development and regulation of blood sugar in human body, normal human body contains 6–7 mg chromium. In the present study, the mean levels of chromium ranged from 1.01 mg/kg in Huangjinxiu of Taiping collage of yuanyang to 2.36 mg/kg in Xinfeng 2 of Hongjingzui of huojia. This is considerably lower than what has been reported in other recent studies. Lin *et al.*²² reported a mean Cr concentration of 0.07 mg/kg in rice available on the Taiwanese market. Gorbunov *et al.*²¹ reported a mean Cr level of 0.16 mg/kg in rice from the Astrakhan region of Russia.

Potassium and sodium :

Potassium and sodium are very important minerals in human body, they work together to control the body's water balance. Sodium and potassium were the main electrolyte in body fluid, which plays an important role in regulating cell, tissue fluid and blood electrolyte balance. The highest mean levels of potassium were found in Zhengdao 19 and Xinfeng 2 with 821.05 and 940.96 mg/kg in Taiping collage of yuanyang, while in other rice the concentrations of potassium are almost no change. Sodium level of 318.99 mg/kg in Xinfeng of 2 Fucun of huojia was markedly higher than the level of 221.78 mg/kg in Xinfeng 4 of Fucun of huojia, and also higher than the mean level of 245.98 mg/kg in other rice.

Other essential elements :

Calcium is one of the extremely important constant element in human body. The highest and lowest values for calcium 147.58 mg/kg in Shengdao 16 of Fucun of huojia and 66.55 mg/kg in Huangjinxiu of Taiping collage of yuanyang. Zinc can increase the sensitivity of the human immune system, also can directly suppress the activity of the virus, so as to enhance the body resistance to disease. Cobalt is an important part of vitamin B12. Cobalt also is an important element in the synthesis of protein and fat. However, all zinc and cobalt contents of samples were not found.

Experimental

Rice samples and treatment :

The samples of Shengdao 16 rice, Xinfeng 4 rice, Xinfeng 2 rice, Huangjingqing rice came from Fucun collage of huojia county in Henan province. The samples of Huangjingqing rice, Xinfeng 2 rice, Zhengdao19 rice came from Hongjingzui collage of huojia county in Henan province. The samples of Zhengdao 19 rice, Xinfeng 2 rice, Huangjinxiu rice came from Taiping collage of yuanyang county in Henan province.

Nine rice samples were washed with tap water to eliminate the air-borne pollutants and then blotted dry with tissue paper, and then dried in an oven at 65 °C until constant weight. At last, rice samples were ground with the grinder.

Dried ground rice samples (0.5000 g) were treated with 10 mL HNO₃ in a Teflon container overnight, then were added to 1 mL H₂O₂ and placed in a microwave digester MAS under a power controlled program optimized. After the end of the microwave digestion procedures, the digestion solution was transferred into the according beakers in order to reduce the acid concentration of digestion solution, and all the beakers were heated by a electric heating plate at 160 °C for 2 h. At last, solutions were transferred to 25 mL volumetric flask and filled up with 2% HNO₃. The optimized operational parameters of the microwave digestion are just shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The optimized operational parameters of the microwave digestion

Procedure	Power (W)	Temperature raise time (min)	Runing temperature (°C)	Holding time (min)
1	800	5	120	3
2	800	3	140	4
3	1600	5	160	16
Cool down			70	20

Reagent and apparatus :

All standard solutions used (0.00, 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00, 8.00 µg/mL) were prepared by diluting 1000 µg/mL stock multi-element standard solution (23 elements) with ultra-pure water for ICP-OES determination. HNO₃ and H₂O₂ were analytical grade. The blank reagent and

standard reference materials GBW10010 rice (from the National Research Center for Standards in China) were included in each sample batch to verify the accuracy and precision of the digestion procedure and subsequent analyses.

Oven (101A-2, Shanghai Laboratory Instrument Factory, China). Grinder (FW-80, Beijing Ever Light Medical Equipment Co. Ltd., China). An ultra-pure water system (SG Ultra Clear system, Wasseraufbereitung and Regenerierstation GmbH, Germany). Optima2100 DV inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer (ICP-OES, Perkin-Elmer Corporation of USA), and MAS microwave digestion system (CEM Corporation of USA).

Determination of essential elements in rice samples :

Essential elements were determined by ICP-OES. ICP-OES settings and operating conditions are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Operating conditions of ICP-OES

Operating condition	Operating parameter
R_f power (W)	1300
Gas flow rate (mL min ⁻¹)	
Coolant gas	15
Auxiliary gas	0.2
Nebuliser gas	0.75
Sample uptake rate (mL min ⁻¹)	1.5
Torch	Fused quartz (radial)
Read time (s)	15
Delay time (s)	25
Wash time (s)	25
Elements monitored (wavelength, nm)	Fe (589.59), Mg (279.08), Mn (257.61), Se (196.02), Ni (231.60), Cu (324.75), K (766.52), Na (589.62), Ca (317.95), Zn (213.87), Co (228.63) and Cr (267.73)

Conclusions

ICP-OES with microwave assisted extraction is suitable for essential metal elements determination. Essential metal elements content varied in a wide range in the nine rice samples. This study is to give important reference value to people due to individual differences by adjusting the diet to complement the different mineral elements.

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